
Managerial Skills among Integrated and Non-Integrated School Heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo, Philippines: A Comparative Study

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ABSTRACT: This descriptive quantitative study aimed to determine the managerial skills of integrated and non-integrated school heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo for the school year 2019-2020. The respondents of the study were the 62 integrated school heads and 62 non-integrated school heads of the Schools Division of Iloilo. The statistical tools used were the frequency counts and percentage, mean, independent t-test and One-Way ANOVA. Results revealed that when the integrated school heads were taken as an entire group and when classified as sex, age, civil status, and years of school head experience the managerial skills of the integrated school heads is in a “high range”. In terms of highest educational attainment, baccalaureate and masters’ degree revealed “high range” managerial skills, while doctorate degree showed “very high range” managerial skills. Results revealed that when the non-integrated school heads were taken as an entire group and when classified as sex, age, civil status, years of school head experience, and highest educational qualification the managerial skills of the integrated school heads is in a “high range”. There were no significant differences on the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of technical when they were taken as a whole and when they were classified according to sex and age.

KEYWORDS: Managerial skills, Integrated school Heads, Non- Integrated School Heads

I. INTRODUCTION

Handling the administration of an educational institution such as a school or college is not among the easiest of jobs as there are a lot of things that need to be taken care, which includes management of learners and staff information, attendance, timetable, and other things. School heads often face new challenges due to education reforms happening in the country.

The value of education particularly in a developing country like the Philippines cannot be underestimated. It is believed as the tool that could transform a person to live a better life and more importantly a socially well-being. Thus, the Education for ALL (EFA) 2015 Plan emphasizes that educational opportunities are channels of learning which can become effective conduits of values orientation, consciousness and information useful and relevant to a wide range of social goals (UNESCO, 2015).

In accordance with the broadening of accessibility to basic education, the program commitment has the following components: establishment of a school in every barangay not having an elementary school and in every town without a high school; organization of multi-grade classrooms; completion of incomplete elementary schools; and provision of basic instructional materials, facilities and equipment at the elementary and high school levels (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), 2015).

Related to the first commitment, several elementary schools nationwide have been converted into integrated schools to make sure that those who graduate from elementary schools who have to travel several kilometres away from the nearest high school will continue schooling (DepEd Order No.91, s.1999). Unfortunately, the transformation of these elementary schools into integrated schools poses interesting challenges to the present school administrators because from managing just an elementary school, they already need to oversee the operation of an elementary and a high school with an added two-year Senior High School in one campus. This means, their responsibilities have become doubled if not multiplied (DepEd Order No. 40, s. 2014). This study aimed to determine the managerial skills among integrated and non-integrated school heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo, Philippines when taken as taken as an entire group and when classified as sex, age, civil status, and years of school head experience.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The purpose of this study is to determine the managerial skills of integrated and non-integrated school heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo for School Year 2019-2020 based on their sex, age, civil status, years of school head experience, and highest educational attainment.

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This study used the descriptive method of research which according to Bary and Gall as cited by David (2013), Guillem (2018) are primarily concerned with finding out “what is”. Moreover, descriptive research involves collecting data in the status of the study. It determined and reported the way things are as well as takes concern with the assessment of attitudes, and opinions, information, conditions, and procedures.

B. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the integrated and non-integrated school heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo classified as to age (40 years old and below and 41 years old and above), sex (male, female), civil status (single, married), years of school head experience (10 years and below and 11 years and above), and highest educational qualification (Baccalaureate, Master’s Degree, and Doctorate Degree).

The entire group consisted of 124 respondents wherein 62 integrated school heads from integrated schools were 50% of the entire group and 62 non-integrated school heads from non-integrated schools were 50% of the entire group. As to sex, 41 of the respondents were male which obtained 33.1% of the whole group, 83 of the respondents were female which obtained 66.9% of the entire group. As to age, 55 of the respondents were 40 years old and below which obtained 44.4% of the entire group, 69 of the respondents were 41 years old and above which obtained 55.6% of the entire group. As to civil status, 59 of the respondents were single which obtained 47.6% of the whole group, 65 of the respondents were married which obtained 52.4% of the entire group. As to years of school head experience, 69 of the respondents has 10 years and below which obtained 55.6% of the whole group, 55 of the respondents has 11 years and above which obtained 44.4% of the entire group. As to highest educational attainment, 66 of the respondents were baccalaureate degree holders which obtained 53.2% of the whole group, 54 of the respondents were master’s degree holders which obtained 43.5% of the entire group, and four (4) were Doctorate Degree holders which obtained 3.3% of the entire group. Table 1 shows the data.

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents

Category	f	%
A. Entire Group	124	100
B. Type of School		
Integrated	62	50
Non- Integrated	62	50
C. Sex		
Male	41	33.1
Female	83	66.9
D. Age		
40 years old and below	55	44.4
41 years old and above	69	55.6
E. Civil Status		
Single	59	47.6
Married	65	52.4
F. Years of School Head Experience		
10 years and below	69	55.6
11 years and above	55	44.4
G. Highest Educational Attainment		
Baccalaureate	66	53.2
Master’s Degree	54	43.5
Doctorate Degree	4	3.3

C. Data Gathering Instruments

The researchers emailed the author Dr. Peter Northouse to use and adopt the questionnaire. Permission was granted by the author through an email and the researchers adopted the eighteen (18) items questionnaire on managerial skills. The questionnaire checklist consisted of two parts: the first part gathered the integrated and non-integrated school heads information about their sex, age, civil status, years of school head experience, highest educational attainment, and type of school while the second part included the school heads’ managerial skills. The respondents were asked to check one of the following responses. It has five options namely: Not True, Seldom True, Occasionally True, Somewhat True, and Very True. The responses were interpreted as follows:

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- Not True means that the school heads do not perform the managerial skill.
- Seldom True means that the school heads rarely perform the managerial skill.
- Occasionally True means that the school heads sometimes but not often perform the managerial skills.
- Somewhat True means that the school heads often or repeatedly performed the managerial skills.
- Occasionally True means that the school heads sometimes but not often perform the managerial skill.
- Very True means that the school heads consistently performed the managerial skills.

Response options ranged from 5 (very true) to 1 (not true). The obtained mean was transformed into an arbitrary scale which was used in the interpretation of the results.

Arbitrary Scale

Mean	Description
4.21-5.00	Very True
3.41-4.20	Seldom True
2.61-3.40	Occasionally True
1.81-2.60	Somewhat True
1.00-1.80	Very true

D. Data Gathering Procedure

To gather the needed data for this research, the researcher first secured a written permit to administer the instrument from the Schools Division Superintendent in the Schools Division of Iloilo then to the integrated and non-integrated school heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo. After the permission was granted, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaire checklist to the integrated and non-integrated school heads in the chosen schools in the Schools Division of Iloilo. In this instrument, the respondents were given ample time to read and answer the items and retrieved them in the agreed time. All the data gathered were encoded, computerized, process, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Managerial Skills of Integrated School Heads in terms of Technical in the Schools Division of Iloilo when Classified as to Age, Sex, Civil Status, Years of School Head Experience and Highest Educational Qualification

The managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of technical was determined using mean and standard deviation. When taken as an entire group the integrated school heads have a “high range” managerial skill in terms of technical (M=23.58, SD=3.05).

When classified as to sex: male (M= 24.52, SD= 3.97); female (M= 23.09, SD=2.36); age: 40 years old and below (M= 23.10, SD= 2.69); 41 years old and above (M= 24.00, SD=3.35); civil status: single (M= 27.74, SD= 2.61); married (M= 24.61, SD=3.27). Those who are single exhibited a “very high range” of managerial skills in terms of Technical, while those who are married exhibited a “high range” of managerial skills. Years of school head experience: 10 years and below (M= 22.88, SD= 2.84); 11 years and above (M= 24.43, SD=3.13). School heads of integrated school who have 10 years and below experience and 11 years and above exhibited “high range of managerial skills” in terms of Technical. But, when classified as to their highest educational qualification: baccalaureate (M= 23.00, SD= 3.10); master’s degree (M= 23.89, SD=2.74); and doctorate degree (M=28.50, SD=3.02), the result shows that baccalaureate and master’s degree holders exhibited the same degree of managerial skills. Likewise, those with doctorate degree exhibited a “very high range” of managerial skills.

This means that almost all integrated school heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo have high range of knowledge and ability to use different techniques to achieve what they want to achieve, except for those school heads with doctorate degree having a very high range of technical skills. The results of this study confirm with the study of Lee (2007) titled “*School Principals’ Effectiveness and Leadership Quality in Educational Management*”, that says there are several critical elements in the school principals’ managerial perspective. One must have good educational background, which includes excellent leadership skills and knowledgeable. Table 2 shows the data.

Table 2: Managerial Skills of Integrated School Heads in Terms of Technical in the Schools Division of Iloilo when Classified as to Age, Sex, Civil Status, Years of School Head Experience and Highest Educational Qualification

Category	N	Mean	SD	Description
A. Entire Group	62	23.58	3.05	High Range
B. Sex				
Male	21	24.52	3.97	High Range
Female	41	23.09	2.36	High Range

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C. Age				
40 years old and below	29	23.10	2.69	High Range
41 years old and above	33	24.00	3.35	High Range
D. Civil Status				
Single	34	27.74	2.61	Very High Range
Married	28	24.61	3.27	High Range
E. Years of School Head Experience				
10 years and below	34	22.88	2.84	High Range
11 years and above	28	24.43	3.13	High Range
F. Highest Educational Attainment				
Baccalaureate	32	23.00	3.10	High Range
Master's Degree	28	23.89	2.74	High Range
Doctorate Degree	2	28.50	3.02	Very High Range

Note: 26-30, Very High Range; 21-25, High Range; 16-20, Moderate Range; 11-15, Low Range; 6-10, Very Low Range

B. Managerial Skills of Non-integrated School Heads in terms of Technical in the Schools Division of Iloilo when Classified as to Age, Sex, Civil Status, Years of School Head Experience and Highest Educational Qualification

The managerial skills of non-integrated school heads in terms of technical were determined using mean and standard deviation. When taken as an entire group the integrated school heads have a high range of managerial skills (M=24.10, SD=2.44). When classified as to sex: male (M= 24.23, SD= 2.66); female (M= 24.19, SD=2.57); age: 40 years old and below (M= 24.00, SD= 2.34); above 40 years old (M= 24.33, SD=2.75); civil status: single (M= 24.00, SD= 2.51); married (M= 24.32, SD=2.64); years of school head experience: 10 years and below (M= 24.05, SD= 2.38); and above 10 years (M= 24.37, SD=2.84); highest educational qualification: baccalaureate (M= 24.23, SD= 2.60); master's degree (M= 24.23, SD=2.53); doctorate degree (M=23.00, SD=4.24), the results of this study affirms the findings of Peterson and Van Fleet (2004) on his study on “*The Ongoing Legacy of RLKatz: An Update Typology of Management Skills*”, that managers should have the following skills: diagnostic, technical, human- analytical, cognitive, communicative, interpersonal, administrative skills, decision making and flexibility skills.

This implies that non-integrated school heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo have high range of Technical skills to perform practical tasks in areas of mechanics, science, mathematics, and information technology. Table 3 shows the data.

Table 3: Managerial Skills of Non-integrated School Heads in Terms of Technical in the Schools Division of Iloilo when Classified as to Age, Sex, Civil Status, Years of School Head Experience, and Highest Educational Qualification

Category	N	Mean	SD	Description
A. Entire Group	62	24.10	2.44	High Range
B. Sex				
Male	20	24.23	2.66	High Range
Female	42	24.19	2.57	High Range
C. Age				
40 years old and below	26	24.00	2.34	High Range
41 years old and above	36	24.33	2.75	High Range
D. Civil Status				
Single	25	24.00	2.51	High Range
Married	37	24.32	2.64	High Range
E. Years of School Head Experience				
10 years and below	35	24.05	2.38	High Range
11 years and above	27	24.37	2.84	High Range
F. Highest Educational Attainment				
Baccalaureate	34	24.23	2.60	High Range
Master's Degree	26	24.23	2.53	High Range
Doctorate Degree	2	23.00	4.24	High Range

Note: 26-30, Very High Range; 21-25, High Range; 16-20, Moderate Range; 11-15, Low Range; 6-10, Very Low Range

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C. Differences on the Managerial Skills of Integrated School Heads in Terms of Technical in the Schools Division of Iloilo when Classified as to Age, Sex, Civil Status and Years of School Head Experience

Computed t-test results revealed that there is no significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of technical between male and female (t- value= 1.77, p-value= 0.081). Likewise, computed t-test revealed no significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of Technical between 40 years old and below and above 40 years old (t-value= -1.158, p-value= 0.251). Further, it also revealed a significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of Technical between single and married (t-value= -2.508, p-value= 0.015). The computed t-test also revealed a significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of Technical between 10 years and below and above 10 years (t-value= -2.038, p-value= 0.046). Thus, the null hypothesis which states that “there are no significant differences in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of technical when they are classified as to sex and age was accepted but rejected when classified as to civil status and years of school head experience.

The findings of this study correspond with the study of Carmeli (2008) in “*The Management Skills and the Performance of Municipal Organization*”, that has evaluated the effects of management skills on the performance of city agencies and has come to the conclusion that management skills (technical - creativity and educational) have an effect on the organization's performance. In the short-term, changes in the management skills can easily create significant changes in the performance level because, the structural changes in addition to the high cost need to spend more time. Table 4 shows the data.

Table 4: Differences on the Managerial Skills of Integrated School Heads in Terms of Technical in the Schools Division of Iloilo when Classified as to Age, Sex, Civil Status, and Years of School Head Experience

Category	N	Mean	t	df	p-value
A. Sex					
Male	21	24.52	1.77	60	0.081
Female	41	23.09			
B. Age					
40 years old and below	29	23.10	1.158	60	0.251
41 years old and above	33	24.00			
C. Civil Status					
Single	34	22.73	2.508	60	0.015*
Married	28	24.60			
D. Years of School Head Experience					
10 years and below	34	22.88	2.038	60	0.046*
11 years and above	28	24.42			

p> .05 not significant at .05 alpha

D. Managerial Skills of Integrated School Heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo in Terms of Technical when Classified as to Highest Educational Qualification

ANOVA result revealed that there is a significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of technical when they are classified as to their highest educational qualification (F= 3.61, p= .033). This means that the managerial skills of the integrated school heads having a baccalaureate, master’s degree, and doctorate degree, in terms of Technical exhibited significant difference in every group. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that “there is no significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of Technical when categorized on their highest educational attainment” was rejected.

The results of this study affirm the study of Purwanto (2001) in “*Principles of Principles and Teaching Evaluation*”, that the quality of education and teaching in schools is influenced by the educational background of the principal, this means that the higher the level of education of a school principal, the higher and better the quality of education and teaching received by the learner and the higher the degree of the community. This implies that highest educational attainment affects managerial skills of integrated school heads of Schools Division of Iloilo in terms of Technical. Table 5 shows the data.

Table 5: Managerial Skills of Integrated School Heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo in Terms of Technical when Classified as to Highest Educational Qualification

Educational Attainment	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	f-ratio	p-value
Between Groups	61.918	2	30.959	3.616	.033*
Within Groups	505.179	59	8.562		
Total	567.097	61			

p> .05 not significant at .05 alpha

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E. Post Hoc for the Differences in Means in the Managerial Skills of Integrated School Heads in Terms of Technical when Classified as to Highest Educational Qualification

Pair-wise comparison using Scheffe Test showed no significant differences between integrated school heads having master’s degree and doctorate degree ($p\text{-value}=.108$), and those with baccalaureate and master’s degree holder ($p\text{-value}=.503$) in their managerial skills in terms of Technical. Significant differences in the managerial skills were observed between school heads with baccalaureate degree and with those school heads having doctorate degree ($p\text{-value}=.043$). Table 6 shows the data.

Table 6: Post Hoc for the Differences in Means in the Managerial Skills of Integrated School Heads in Terms of Technical when Classified as to Highest Educational Qualification

Managerial Skills	Highest Educational Qualification	Mean Difference	p-value
Baccalaureate	Master’s Degree	.892	.503
	Doctorate Degree	5.500	.043*
Doctorate Degree	Master’s Degree	4.607	.108

$p > .05$ not significant at .05 alpha

F. Differences on the Managerial Skills of Non-integrated School Heads in Terms of Technical in the Schools Division of Iloilo when Classified as to Age, Sex, Civil Status, and Years of School Head Experience

Computed t-test revealed that there is no significant difference in the managerial skills of non-integrated school heads in terms of technical between male and female ($t\text{-value}=.196$, $p\text{-value}=0.846$) school heads. Likewise, computed t-test revealed no significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads between 40 years old and below and above 40 years old ($t\text{-value}=.499$, $p\text{-value}=0.622$). It also revealed no significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads between single and married ($t\text{-value}=0.483$, $p\text{-value}=0.631$). Further, computed t-test revealed no significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads between 10 years and below and above 10 years ($t\text{-value}=.471$, $p\text{-value}=0.639$). Thus, the null hypothesis which states that “there are no significant differences in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of technical when they are classified as to sex, age, civil status, and years of school head experience” was accepted.

The results of this study contradict with the study of Nitisemito (2009), titled “*Personnel Management (Resource, Management, Power, People)*”, that work experience is something or ability possessed by employees in carrying out the tasks assigned to him. With quite a long experience and quite a lot, it is expected that they will have a greater ability than those without experience. This implies that the variables had no influence as regards to managerial skills of non-integrated school heads of Schools Division of Iloilo in terms of Technical. Table 7 shows the data.

Table 7: Differences on the Managerial Skills of Non-integrated School Heads in Terms of Technical in the Schools Division of Iloilo when Classified as to Age, Sex, Civil Status, and Years of School Head Experience

Category	N	Mean	T	df	p- value
A. Sex					
Male	20	24.10	.196	60	0.846
Female	42	24.23			
B. Age					
40 years old and below	26	24.00	.499	60	0.622
41 years old and above	36	24.33			
C. Civil Status					
Single	25	24.00	.483	60	0.631
Married	37	24.32			
D. Years of School Head Experience					
10 years and below	35	24.05	.471	60	0.639
11 years and above	27	24.37			

$p > .05$ not significant at .05 alpha

G. Managerial Skills in Terms of Technical of Non-integrated School Heads when Classified as to Highest Educational Qualification

ANOVA result revealed that there is no significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads in terms of Technical when categorized on their highest educational qualification ($F=.216$, $p\text{-value}=.807$). Therefore, null hypothesis which

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states that “there is no significant difference in the managerial skills of integrated school heads when categorized on their highest educational qualification” was accepted.

This finding affirms the study of Kartini et al. (2019) titled, “*The Influence of Principal’s Leadership, Academic Supervision, and Professional Competence Toward Teachers’ Performance*”, and Murtiningsih et al (2019) titled, “*The Correlation Between Supervision of Headmaster and Interpersonal Communication with Work Ethos of the Teacher*” which found out that school principals have heavy duty and responsibility, so ideally the principal must have adequate academic qualifications, work experience and positive work motivation. Table 8 shows the data.

Table 8: Managerial Skills in Terms of Technical of Non-integrated School Heads when Classified as to Highest Educational Qualification

Educational Attainment	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	f-ratio	p-value
Between Groups	2.944	2	1.472	.216	.807
Within Groups	402.733	59	6.826		
Total	405.677	61			

p > .05 not significant at .05 alpha

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions have been drawn:

Majority of the integrated and non-integrated school heads possessed a high range of managerial skills. It can be concluded that integrated and non-integrated school heads in the Schools Division of Iloilo, regardless of their sex, age, civil status, years of school head experience, and highest educational attainment possess “high range” of managerial skills to perform their duties well.

It can also be concluded that, regardless of the type of school, integrated or non-integrated, school heads possess almost all the needed managerial skills expected for every school head. Managerial skills are the knowledge and ability of the individuals in a managerial position to fulfill some specific management activities or tasks. This knowledge and ability can be learned and practiced. Every school administrator can become better in management when they will learn and practice the behaviors, methods, and techniques of other successful school administrators. If they do other successful school heads, they will soon get the results that others school heads get.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings of this study, the researcher offers the following recommendations:

The findings of the study may be known to integrated and non-integrated school heads, although majority of them have high range managerial skills, they may continue to pursue higher studies to equip them with advance knowledge, skills and competence to bring their managerial skills to a very high range so that they can perform their duties better. Integrated and non-integrated school heads may practice the three managerial skills, which are conceptual, interpersonal, and technical skills. They may enhance managerial skills in terms of technical skills by conducting seminars and workshops in line with their insufficient skills. School administrators should enhance their managerial skills for the delivery of good services in school administration. School administrators may always be guided by their managerial skills to be applied in their workplace taking into consideration their leadership strengths and weaknesses.

Education program supervisors and public Schools district supervisors may develop enhancement activities through trainings, seminars, programs, or simply extend technical assistance to school administrators especially the newly hired school heads through the data captured in this research.

Teachers may also be allowed to attend related seminars and conferences to further develop their knowledge of these managerial skills and apply them to the workplace. Future researcher/s may replicate this study using experimental method or any appropriate method which will focus on how to enhance one’s managerial skills.

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